

TYPES OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES

Denau Institute of Enterpreneurship and Pedagogy

Philology Faculty 4th grade, 407-group students

Abduvahobova Sevara

Abdug'aniyeva Izzatoy

Abduhalimova Mahbuba

Abdullayeva Mohira

Abduvaliyev Shahbozbek

Almardanov Mirjalol

ANNOTATION: *English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has been a prevailing trend in language instruction for several years. The concepts of ESP are integral to the design of a syllabus or the development of teaching materials for a certain course or study. Traditionally, ESP classes were primarily designed for intermediate or advanced adult learners. Currently, numerous students can commence their study of academic or vocational English at a younger age and with a lower skill level. A needs analysis, integral to the concepts of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), is conducted to identify the requirements of the course participants. This study consists of three sections: the nature of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), requirements analysis in ESP, and ESP within the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL).*

Key words: *English Language Teaching, English for Specific Purposes*

INTRODUCTION: Teaching language for specific purposes (LSP) can be traced back to the Greek and Roman empires. Similarly, Strevens asserts that the history of LSP extends back "at least half a century." English for Specific Purposes (ESP) originated post-World War II and was characterized as an unplanned and incoherent movement, arising from several converging movements. ESP has functioned and operated in varied ways around the world, "but we can identify three main reasons common to the emergence of all ESP.": the demands of a brave new world, a revolution in language, and a new focus on the learner.

Some linguists, being conscious of the world's changes, began to focus their studies on how language is employed in real settings. The traditional approach to language research focused on the grammatical rules that control language usage. However, it was shown that discourses differ according to settings. Then, the teaching and learning techniques were reconstructed according to the language specificities of each situation. The English needed by engineers, surgeons, linguists, or officers “could be identified by analyzing the linguistic characteristics of their specialist area of work or study”. “Tell me what you need English for and I will tell you the English that you need became the guiding principle of ESP”.

In the same period, learners' motivation towards mastering a foreign language was the topic research of the educational psychologists, who discovered the employment of diverse learning strategies by learners; they had varied attitudes, requirements, and interests. The notion was built on the statement of tell me what you need English for and I will tell you the English you need. It was a logical outgrowth of this principle to plan individual courses for each group of specific learners. Strevens notes: “...the existence of a major “tide” in the educational thought, in all countries and affecting all subjects. The movement referred to is the global trend towards “learner-centered education”. Like the globe, language study and concepts of education fundamentally changed, the English language teaching evolved with it, and knew the birth of teaching English for Specific Purposes which is viewed as the direct result of the world evolution. “ESP is not a monolithic universal phenomenon”; it has developed at different paces in different places. The methodologies that we shall explain can be found operating somewhere in the world at present. This concept departed from the principle that English of a certain scientific differs from each other in terms of its grammatical and lexical elements of the registers. Register analyses in ESP were geared for the pedagogic aim, i.e. making the ESP course more relevant to learners” needs, not intended for discussing the nature of registers of English per se. The fundamental objective of an ESP course was to develop a syllabus that gave a high priority to the language forms students would meet in their field and turn would give low priority to forms they would not meet. Register analysis found that there was very little that was distinctive in the sentence grammar of scientific English beyond a

propensity to favor particular forms such as the present simple tense, the passive voice, and noun compound. The purpose of target situation analysis is to take the current information and set it on a more scientific basis, by building processes for linking language analysis more closely to learners' reasons for learning. There is a purpose of the ESP course that supports this phase, the purpose is to enable learners to function in situations in which the learners will use the language they are learning, then the ESP course design process should proceed by first identifying the target situation and then carrying out the right analysis of the linguistic parts of that situation. It will compose the syllabus of the ESP course. This procedure is known as "needs analysis". What had been done earlier in the piecemeal method became something systematized and learner requirements were seemingly placed at the center of the course design process.

Previously, in the origins of ESP, we understood that three forces had a function in ESP and became its features, they were needs, new thoughts about language, and new concepts about learning. We use all the approaches so far based on the descriptions of language use and the concern in each case is with describing what people do with language, but the concern is not actually on the language use only, our concern should be with language learning too because a truly valid approach to ESP must be based on an understanding of the processes of language learning. With this statement, it gets us to this fifth level of ESP growth. The importance and the ramifications of the distinction that we have created between language use and language learning will hopefully become evident for us to grasp each of the stages of ESP development. David Carter describes three forms of ESP:

English as a restricted language

English for Academic and Occupational Purposes English with specific topics.

The language used by air traffic controllers or waiters are instance of English as a restricted language. Mackay and Mount Ford effectively explain the difference between restricted language and language with this statement: ... the language of international air-traffic control could be regarded as 'unique', in the sense that the repertoire required by the controller is rigorously constrained and can be correctly identified situationally, as might be the linguistic needs of a dining-room waiter or air-hostess. However, such constrained repertoires are not languages, just as a

tourist phrase book is not grammar. Knowing a narrow 'language' would not allow the speaker to communicate successfully in unexpected situations, or in contexts beyond the vocational area. The second category of ESP established by Carter is English for Academic and Occupational Purposes. In the 'Tree of ELT', ESP is split down into three branches: a) English for Science and Technology (EST), b) English for Business and Economics (EBE), and c) English for Social Studies (ESS). Each of these topic areas is further divided into two branches: English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Occupational Purposes (EOP). An example of EOP for the EST branch is 'English for Technicians' whereas an example of EAP for the EST branch is 'English for Medical Studies'.

Hutchinson and Waters do note that there is not a clear-cut distinction between EAP and EOP: “People can work and study simultaneously; it is also likely that in many cases the language learned for immediate use in a study environment will be used later when the student takes up, or returns to, a job”. Perhaps this explains Carter's rationale for putting EAP and EOP under the same sort of ESP. It appears that Carter is saying that the final objective of both EAP and EOP are one and the same: employment. However, while the final aim is identical, the means employed to attain the end are very different indeed. The third and last sort of ESP outlined by Carter is English with specialized subjects. Carter notes that it is only here the focus switches from purpose to issue. This sort of ESP is uniquely focused on predicted future English demands of, for example, scientists seeking English for postgraduate reading courses, visiting conferences, or working in foreign institutions. However, this is not a separate form of ESP. Rather it is an integral component of ESP courses or programs that focus on situational language. This situational language has been determined based on the interpretation of data from a needs analysis of real language used in target employment contexts.

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